

I-CISK
HUMAN CENTRED CLIMATE SERVICES

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I-CISK platform - Technical Specification

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Innovating Climate services through Integrating Scientific and local Knowledge

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Executive Summary

Nowadays, various research studies monitor and predict the impact of the upcoming climate change (CC) and explore corresponding human adaptation strategies. Nevertheless, the knowledge generated in these studies is rarely translated into a form that can easily be accessed by society. Above that, the potential that results from combining scientific knowledge with stakeholder experiences is often not exploited. This deliverable describes current efforts with respect to the development of a cloud-based web platform that aims to address the challenges mentioned above. The so-called Climate Service (CS) platform is developed in the course of the I-CISK project and will provide climate indicators to stakeholders with various professions (e.g. from the field of agriculture, tourism or also policy makers). The format in which these indicators are provided will be adapted to the stakeholders needs and the indicators will be derived based on local data resources as well as available large CS providers.

This deliverable is structured following the widely accepted standard of the arc42 template [11] for the documentation of software architecture¹. It starts from a discussion of the stakeholder requirements with respect to the CS platform which have been identified in bilateral meetings with the leaders of the I-CISK Living Labs (LL). In this context, the deliverable also touches shortly on the process of how the requirements have been elaborated. Based on the stakeholder requirements, quality goals for the CS platform are derived and major architectural decision and constraints are summarised. To assure the realisation of the quality goals, a framework and a timeline for a thorough testing procedure are proposed.

The CS platform will connect various data sources and CS modeling tools for the indicator calculation. The most important interfaces are discussed in the further context of this deliverable. A more detailed insight into the design of the individual platform components is presented as well as a runtime scenario which, for the example of the Italian LL, shows how the individual components of the platform will interact in case of an exemplary request for indicator calculation.

¹For this deliverable, the original arc42 template has been adjusted to the scope of the I-CISK project such that the current document exhibits modifications with respect to the original.

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1. Introduction and Goals

This document describes the Technical Specification, Architecture and IT requirements of the I-CISK platform. It follows the widely accepted standard of the arc42 template [11] for the documentation of software architecture². I-CISK will develop and deploy an innovative cloud-based I-CISK web platform to support co-produced human-centred CS. This cloud-based I-CISK web platform will incorporate the innovative tools and methods developed in I-CISK for integrating local knowledge to transform scientific data. Following the co-production approach, this will be developed to meet the needs of the LLs and applied to establish the pre-operational climate-service infrastructure (CSIS) launched in each of the LLs.

The platform is developed around highly modular components:

- Front-end components that allow users to visualise scientifically and user-tailored sub-seasonal to seasonal forecasts, decadal predictions and climate projections of the identified target variables. Additional components will allow to access and visualize information related to exposure, vulnerability and corresponding uncertainties. The front-end modules will also provide means to evaluate scenarios with different adaptation options by the users, in order to interactively develop strategies that reduce risk for multiple sectors of interest and achieve a resilient future. These front-end components support establishing of the communication methods to best suit end-user needs identified in the co-design process, and provide access using the medium most appropriate to the end-user (web based and/or mobile applications).
- Back-end components that support the integration of local knowledge and data, and embed Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) using open standards (WPS, WFS, WCS, API Processes ...) from the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) to maximise access and integration of data from external data providers such as Copernicus as well as initiatives and platforms of the Group of Earth Observations (GEO). A particular focus is set on the integration of data from the Copernicus Data Store (CDS) via the CDS API but also other Copernicus services such as the Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS) or the Copernicus Climate Change Service sectorial (C3S) will be reviewed in this respect. Further possible data sources constitute the Subseasonal-to-Seasonal Prediction Project (S2S) as well as space data from the European Space Agency (ESA), Eurostat or EU WISE. The integration of these data sources will facilitate access to this knowledge for a wide range of users. Access to the modules of the platform will be (i) through a set of open access and executable Python and R scripts organised in Jupyter notebooks (lightweight integration) or (ii) fully embedded in a cloud environment or (iii) through an easy to use front-end (user interface in a web browser) for users with few programming skills. This innovative approach will make it possible for users to choose from and modify the predetermined climate hazard and risk scenarios and to run models either with pre-loaded or with their own hazard forcing and vulnerability data. The I-CISK CSIS platform is intended to be integrated with platforms such as Climate-ADAPT and the cloud-based Adaptation Space developed in the context for the Mission on Climate Adaptation and Societal Transformation.

The I-CISK platform will be developed following the Agile implementation approach with several iterative upgrades through a continuous feedback loop with the end-users in the LLs (WP1), for this reason this document will be periodically revised and updated.

²For this deliverable, the original arc42 template has been adjusted to the scope of the I-CISK project such that the current document exhibits modifications with respect to the original.

Figure 1: Example schemas which have been used in workshops between the LL leaders and the platform developers to identify the stakeholder requirements regarding the workflow of the indicator calculation (back-end). For a description of the individual components it is referred to the main text.

2. Requirements Overview

The Climate Service for the I-CISK project aims to fulfill the following goals:

- provide access to climate and environmental data both from external services (e.g. the Copernicus Program), and established providers like the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) or the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI)) as well as a variety of local data sources;
- integrate different types of local knowledge to allow for triangulation with scientific data;
- integrate analysis chains for indicator calculations which are developed in the I-CISK working packages (WPs) WP3 and WP4;
- provide visualisation tools for the indicators;
- provide stakeholders with the possibility to easily extend the existing functionality by modifying and adding individual components as well as setting up a new CS with a dedicated AUTO CS Composer.

The main components of the cloud-web platform are:

- API components connecting external databases with relevant climatic and socio-economic data and information (e.g. Copernicus, GEOSS, EU-WISE);
- API components to integrate and upload local knowledge and local data about climate and the social economy;
- back-end components allowing to embed the intelligence developed by WP3 and WP4 for each LL, including methods for downscaling, post-processing and impact modeling;
- front-end GUI components such as web mapping, data visualization and interactive web tools, providing capabilities to support the communication and visualisation of climate information CS through web and mobile apps as identified in WP2 and WP3, and using the format appropriate to the end-user;
- a front-end to the platform that allows users less acquainted with programming to build custom CS through an innovative AUTO CS Composer.

2.1. Requirement Analysis

The stakeholder requirements with regards to the CS platform have been identified in a two-step process. First, workshops with the stakeholders from each LL and the LL leaders have been organised to collect the stakeholders' needs. Following up on that, bilateral meetings between the LL leaders and the CS platform developers have been performed to translate these requirements into specifications of the platform architecture. As a basis for the discussion, a schema as presented in Figs. 1 and 2 has been used to draft the workflows for the calculation of the individual indicators. The schema distinguishes between components that need to be considered for the **back-end**, i.e.

- Climate Data Hindcast/Forecast Providers (the external data resources excluding local resources),
- Local Data Knowledge ECV (the local data resources, ECV = essential climate variable),
- EVC/Indicators (the target variables),
- Connector (the way to link the above mentioned data),
- Data Type (the data types of the indicators),
- Time Scenario (the time periods over which the indicators are aggregated),

Figure 2: Example schemas which have been used in workshops between the LL leaders and the platform developers to identify the stakeholder requirements regarding the indicator visualisation (front-end). For a description of the individual components it is referred to the main text.

- Climate Models (models necessary to obtain the target indicators),
- Climate Adaptation/Impact Models (models which investigate the climate response of indicators to adaptation strategies),
- Operation Mode - Climate and Adaptation/Impact Models and
- Climate Model and Adaptation/Impact Model Providers (external services or I-CISK WPs that provide the models).

and components which are relevant for the **front-end**, i.e.

- Visualization Containers (the vehicle we provide the service through, e.g. Story maps of Dashboard),
- Visualization Tools (visual elements such as graphs, maps, time series etc..),
- Visualization Tool Providers (external services or I-CISK WPs that provide the visualization tools),
- Web Service (the way we provide the service ,e.g. jupyter notebook or web service).

2.2. Summary: requirements regarding CS architecture

Following up on the process described in the previous paragraph, the expectations of the stakeholders with respect to the CS platform have been summarised in Tab. 1.

Table 1: Selection of stakeholders for each LL together with their expectations regarding the CS functionality and architecture. If there is a focus on a particular group of stakeholders, this group is marked by (*).

Living Lab	Stakeholder profession	Expectations regarding CS platform
Spain (LL1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Olive Farmers • Dairy Farmers on Oak-/Grassland • Policy makers (water authorities) 	develop full CS that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provides a mobile app • provides weekly and long-term forecasts of ECV and indicators (drought related)
Italy (LL2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional Gov. (*) • Regional Environmental Agency • Irrigation consortia (*) • Private energy Co. • Multi Utility companies 	connect to a CS that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • is accessible through simple interface • provides daily to weekly river discharge forecast in a river (single station) • connects to local data and selected upstream services • can be replicated in similar contexts
Netherland (LL3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers (Pub assoc., private companies) • policy makers • Recreat. shipping assoc. (pub./private) 	connect to a CS that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provides daily to seasonal to CC projections of a set of ECV and indicators (drought related) • connects to local stations and multiple upstream services • embeds and climate/ economic models
Greece (LL4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • development company of Crete responsible for water management (*) • NGOs • municipality of port Rethimno • Greek National tourism organization • representatives of luxury hotel sector 	develop full CS that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provides forecasts on time scales from monthly to seasonal • provides climate projections • connects to local weather stations and selected upstream services • embeds climate/ economic models
Hungary (LL5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipalities • Citizen assoc. • University • Private companies (tech. provider) 	develop full CS that <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provides near real time and on demand projections of forecast of ECV and indicators related air quality / temperature • connects to local weather stations, lot and sensors , weather, services and upstream CS • embeds adaptation models

Living Lab	Stakeholder profession	Expectations regarding CS platform
Georgia (LL6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Env. • National Env. Ag. • Public bodies • University • Citizen organisations 	<p>connect to CS that</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • is accessible through web interface and can generate reports • provides weekly to long term river discharge forecast and other related ECV variables in a river (multiple locations) • connects to local data and selected upstream services • embeds climate/ economic models
Lesotho (LL7)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Disaster Management Team • District Disaster Management Team • Community Based Disaster Response Teams • Village Disaster Management Teams • National University of Lesotho 	<p>connect to an existing CS i.e.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provide WMS that can be accessed by existing multi-active platform via an API • set up data analysis pipeline for weekly to seasonal forecasts that can be integrated in the product Impact Based Forecasting (IBF)

2.3. Outlook: requirements regarding indicator visualisation

For the identification of the stakeholder requirements with respect to the visualisation of the climate indicators, further workshops between stakeholders and the LL leaders as well as the LL leaders and the platform developers are foreseen. As a first step, the stakeholders will be asked to write user stories which provide information about the role of the stakeholder, the visualisation requirements and the purpose of the visualisation. One example for the Spanish LL could be the following:

As a livestock farmer (*stakeholder role*),

I would like to have a visualisation where I can view the historic time-series for temperature or precipitation data from the drought of the 1990s alongside the current temperature and precipitation forecast (*visualisation requirements*)

so that I can make informed decisions about my farming practices (*purpose*).

Based on the resulting user stories, examples with mock-up visualisations will be prepared that will then be discussed in bilateral meetings between the LL leaders and the platform developers. Some first visualisation examples that will be used as inputs for the respective discussions are shown in Figs. 3 to 5.

Figure 3: Visualisation example for the comparison of past and future precipitation on a map for the LL Spain.

Figure 4: Visualisation example for the comparison of two annual time series of temperature data for the LL Spain.

Figure 5: Visualisation example for an ensemble of streamflow seasonal forecasts for a Georgian watershed.

3. Quality goals and test plan

3.1. Quality goals

The quality goals for the CS architecture which have been derived from the stakeholder requirements are summarised in Tab. 2.

Table 2: Summary of quality goals for the CS architecture.

Scenario ID	Scenario
SC1	The visualisation of the climate indicators is comprehensive and adapted to the stakeholders needs such that the CS users can interpret the results without the need for further background knowledge.
SC2	Models and data are integrated in the CS in a modular way such that individual components can be combined for the calculation of different indicators in a flexible way and further components can be added without changing the core architecture.
SC3	The AUTO CS Composer enables stakeholders without computational background knowledge to combine different data sets and analysis steps to build their own tailored CS.
SC4	The software is well documented and easy to operate such that stakeholders with reasonable background knowledge can extend the software functionality of the CS also after the project duration without further support.

3.2. Test plan

To ensure that the I-CISK cloud web application meets the technical specifications and IT requirements and provides a robust and reliable platform for co-produced human-centred CS, the following tests will be performed.

- **Functionality Testing:** This test will verify that all the components of the I-CISK platform work as intended. It will test both the front-end and back-end components of the platform to ensure that the system functions correctly and accurately. The tests will include data validation, data processing, and system integration testing.
 - **Unit testing:** Develop a set of test cases for each individual module of the platform. Test each module to ensure that it functions correctly on its own.
 - **Integration testing:** Test the modules together to ensure that they work together and that data can be exchanged correctly.
 - **System testing:** Test the entire platform to ensure that it functions as a complete system and meets the technical specifications.
- **Performance Testing:** This test will evaluate the system's performance under different conditions, such as high traffic or heavy usage. The test will measure the response time of the platform and identify any bottlenecks that may affect the system's performance. It will help ensure that the system can handle the expected load and provide a satisfactory user experience.
 - **Load testing:** Develop a script that simulates heavy loads on the platform. Monitor the platform's response and analyze the results to identify any bottlenecks or limitations.
 - **Stress testing:** Develop a script that tests the platform beyond its capacity. Monitor the platform's response and analyze the results to identify any issues or failures.

- Endurance testing: Develop a script that tests the platform over extended periods. Monitor the platform's performance and analyze the results to ensure that it can perform consistently and reliably.
- Security Testing: This test will assess the platform's security measures and identify any vulnerabilities that may exist. It will test the platform's authentication and authorization processes, data encryption, and access controls. The test will ensure that the platform can protect sensitive data and user information.
 - Penetration testing: Develop a script that attempts to hack or exploit the platform. Monitor the platform's response and analyze the results to identify any vulnerabilities or security issues.
 - Authentication and authorization testing: The platform's authentication and authorization processes are tested to ensure that only authorized users can access sensitive data. Develop a script that tests the platform's authentication and authorization processes. Ensure that only authorized users can access sensitive data.
 - Data protection testing: The platform's data encryption and access controls are tested to ensure that sensitive data is protected. Develop a script that tests the platform's data encryption and access controls. Ensure that sensitive data is protected and that access controls are working as intended.
- Compatibility Testing: This test will evaluate the platform's compatibility with different web browsers, operating systems, and devices. It will test the platform on different environments and configurations to ensure that it works correctly across a range of systems.
 - Browser testing: The platform is tested on different web browsers to ensure that it functions correctly across multiple platforms.
 - Operating system testing: The platform is tested on different operating systems to ensure that it functions correctly across multiple environments.
 - Device testing: The platform is tested on different devices to ensure that it functions correctly across different screen sizes and resolutions.
- Integration Testing: This test will evaluate the integration of the I-CISK platform with external data providers and platforms. It will test the compatibility and accuracy of the data exchange processes and ensure that the platform can access and integrate data from external sources correctly.
 - API testing: The APIs that connect the platform to external data sources are tested to ensure that data can be exchanged correctly. Develop a script that tests the APIs that connect the platform to external data sources. Ensure that data can be exchanged correctly.
 - Platform integration testing: The platform is tested for compatibility with external platforms.
- Regression Testing: This test will verify that any modifications or changes to the platform do not cause any unintended consequences or issues. It will test the platform's functionality, performance, and security after any updates or modifications to ensure that the system remains stable and reliable.
 - Functional testing: The platform's functionality is tested after any updates or modifications to ensure that it still functions correctly. Develop a set of test cases to ensure that the platform's functionality still works correctly after any updates or modifications.
 - Performance testing: The platform's performance is tested after any updates or modifications to ensure that it still performs satisfactorily. Develop a script to test the platform's performance after any updates or modifications.
 - Security testing: The platform's security measures are tested after any updates or modifications to ensure that there are no vulnerabilities or issues. Develop a script to test the platform's security measures after any updates or modifications.
- Usability Testing: This test will evaluate the ease of use and user-friendliness of the front-end components of the I-CISK platform. It will involve a group of end-users who will perform a series of tasks on the platform to determine if they can interact with the system easily and intuitively. This test will help identify any usability issues and provide insight into how to improve the platform's user experience.

Table 3: Summary of qualitative KPIs for testing procedure.

Test Type	Qualitative KPI
Usability Testing	User satisfaction, task success rate, time on task
Functionality Testing	Test case pass rate, defect density, code coverage
Performance Testing	Response time, throughput, resource utilization
Security Testing	Vulnerability detection rate, threat level
Compatibility Testing	Browser/OS/device compatibility, functionality
Integration Testing	API functionality, external platform compatibility
Regression Testing	Test case pass rate after updates, bug reintroduction

Table 4: Summary of specific KPIs for testing procedure.

Test Name	KPI	Acceptance Criteria
Unit Testing	Code Coverage	80% or above
Integration Testing	Error rate	0% error rate
End-to-End Testing	Response Time	< 10 minutes
Load Testing	Throughput	10 requests per second
Security Testing	Vulnerability Scan	No high-risk issues
Accessibility Testing	WCAG Compliance	Level AA
Usability Testing	Task Completion Rate	> 80%
Performance Testing	Concurrent Users	10 concurrent users

- Task-based testing: Set up a list of tasks that end-users should be able to perform on the platform. Observe and record the end-user's interactions and feedback as they attempt to complete the tasks. Analyze the feedback to identify any issues or areas for improvement
- Heuristic evaluation: Identify a set of established usability principles to evaluate the platform against. Have usability experts evaluate the platform based on these principles and provide feedback and suggestions for improvement.
- User satisfaction surveys: Develop a survey to gather feedback from end-users on their satisfaction with the platform. Analyze the survey results to identify any issues or areas for improvement.

Tab. 3 provides the qualitative key performance indicators (KPIs) that will be monitored to measure whether individual tests are passed successfully. Also, specific acceptance criteria have been defined for several of the tests. These are summarised in Tab. 4.

3.2.1. Test timeline

The test implementation timeline is reported below:

Month 24-27:

- Planning and requirements gathering
- Establish testing objectives and goals
- Define testing strategy and test plan

Month 27-29:

- Usability testing (task-based testing, heuristic evaluation, user satisfaction surveys)
- Initial functionality testing (unit testing)

Month 29-31:

- Performance testing (load testing, stress testing)
- Integration testing (API testing, platform integration testing)

Month 31-33:

- Security testing (penetration testing, authentication and authorization testing, data protection testing)
- Compatibility testing (browser testing, operating system testing, device testing)

Month 33-38:

- Continued testing of all categories (functionality, performance, security, compatibility)
- Regression testing (functional testing, performance testing, security testing)
- Address any issues or bugs found during testing

Month 38-40:

- Retest any areas that had significant issues during initial testing
- Conduct final rounds of testing

Month 40-42:

- Analyze test results and create a final report
- Provide recommendations for improvement
- Submit final report to stakeholders

4. Architecture constraints and fundamental decisions

To meet the quality goals SC2 - SC4 which have been defined in Sect. 3, the following constraints will be considered for the design of the platform architecture:

- the platform will be developed using only open-source components such that also the final infrastructure can be provided under an open-source license; and
- the implementation will follow the standards [8] defined by the OGC and INSPIRE implementing rules [5] to assure interoperability and accessibility e.g. by using the established and self-descriptive data format netCDF [12] for data transfer between platform components.

In addition, the following solution strategies will be applied:

- the system infrastructure will be deployed within a cloud to allow for flexible computing resources and data storage;
- individual components of the platform will run in independent Docker containers [7] to separate their deployment from system dependencies;
- the ETL (extract, transform, load) design pattern will be implemented which is well suited for the processing and analysis of versatile data sources.

Figure 6: A blackbox diagram showing the major interfaces of the CS to model and data providers. The user can access the CS via a GUI and a RESTful API.

Regarding the choice of the cloud service provider, two options are currently under consideration: the Open Telekom Cloud (OTC) as well as the Amazon Web Services (AWS). The AWS come with a large set of functionalities and the usage of these services is common practice. On the other hand, the sovereignty and independence of the CS platform will be strengthened by choosing an European service provider as the OTC. In addition, advantages (e.g. short data access times) may arise if services by the successor of the Data and Information Access Services (DIAS)³ need to be integrated into the CS platform as also this successor is planned to be build on the OTC.

5. Context and Scope

Fig. 6 shows the pivotal interfaces of the CS platform to external components. The platform will integrate external climate modeling tools as well as external data sources and will connect them to climate models that run within the platform. It will calculate the required climate indicators and will provide them to the CS user via a graphical user interface (GUI) or a RESTful API.

Via the GUI, users will be able to initiate the calculation of specific indicators and request the visualisation of the results in a web browser. Thereby, the CS for each living lab will be available via a separate endpoint. The GUI will also encompass the AUTO CS Composer which will enable users to build their own dedicated CSs by chaining individual modeling steps and selecting specific data sets. The REST API will allow for the integration of services provided by the I-CISK framework (e.g. as WMS) into already existing external services.

Several of the LLs require datasets from the Copernicus Earth Observation programme and SMHI for their indicator calculations. Data from Copernicus will be accessed via an API whereas data from SMHI is available from an ftp server. The CS platform will be designed such that also further established data providers can be connected to the web framework throughout the project. Local data will come in various data formats and access modes. The corresponding interfaces will be specified in detail in the further course of the I-CISK project.

The climate modeling tools will either be fully integrated in the CS software as individual software modules or they will wrapped by an API such that they can be accessed by the CS via an API requests.

³DIAS comprises five online platforms that provide access to data and information from the different Copernicus services [3].

6. Building Block View

This section describes the current status of the architecture design starting from the presentation of the major building blocks (i.e. the “Whitebox Overall System”) and, further on, going into more and more detail on the individual “Whitebox” components .

6.1. Whitebox Overall System – Level 1

Fig. 7 illustrates the Level 1 components of the CS platform. The major responsibilities of the corresponding building blocks are

- **GeoNode web framework:** GeoNode is a web application that provides basic functionalities for the development of spatial data infrastructures based on open sources software [4]. For the CS platform, the available features will be extended and modified according to the architecture requirements. The major responsibilities of the GeoNode module include the visualisation of climate indicators via a GUI on the one hand and the provision of an access point to I-CISK web map services and data resources via an REST API on the other hand. GeoNode also provides data and task management tools.
- **WP3 visualisation toolbox:** The visualisation examples developed by WP3 of the I-CISK project will be integrated in the GeoNode web framework. In case compatibility issues arise with the GeoNode application, the corresponding visualisation tools are kept as a separate toolbox.
- **Internal local data:** For several LLs (e.g. Italy), local data will be uploaded manually to the CS platform and will be stored on internal capacities.
- **Data Analysis Tool:** The calculation of the climate indicators is performed in the Data Analysis Tool. Whereas for some indicators the respective models will run as components within the I-CISK platform, the estimation of other parameters requires the connection of external climate models. The corresponding interfaces will be defined in the further course of the I-CISK project.

All components will either be deployed using the OTC or the AWS cloud.

6.2. Whitebox Components – Level 2

6.2.1. GeoNode web framework

Fig. 8 shows the decomposition of the GeoNode framework into the components that will be used for the I-CISK platform. These components have the following responsibilities:

- **GUI:** The GUI enables the CS user to request the calculation and visualisation of particular indicators. It allows for interactive adjustment of calculation constraints. For example, it allows the user to change the time period over which data is aggregated for a selection of indicators. The GUI will be implemented as web application that can be accessed on mobile devices.
- **REST API:** The REST API provides an access point for external services to the CS platform.
- **Internal local data:** Local data that is uploaded manually to the CS platform is stored in a PostgreSQL data base in case of vector data and in the file system in case of raster data. Also, meta data will be stored in the PostgreSQL data base.
- **Task Manager:** Tasks that need to be executed on a regular basis (e.g. regular updates from local data resources) can be scheduled in GeoNode using a combination of Celery [10] and RabbitMQ [1]. Whereas Celery constitutes a task queue, RabbitMQ works as a message broker.
- **GeoServer:** Data sources are accessed and published via a GeoServer [9]. This goes for data from external data sources as well as data which is stored within the CS platform. GeoServer is able to convert between different data formats and implements OGC standards.

Figure 7: A whitebox diagram showing the four major components of the CS platform: the web platform, the Data Analysis Tool, the AUTO CS composer and Indicator visualisation tools.

Figure 8: Whitebox architecture diagram of the GeoNode web framework.

Figure 9: Whitebox architecture diagram of the Data Analysis Tool.

- **Data Ingestor:** It is well possible that some local data sources provide data in formats that can not be handled by GeoServer. This is why, the data ingestor component will read the data from the various resources and convert it in a way that it can be processed by GeoServer. The data ingestor will also harmonises the meta data such that it complies to OGC standards.
- **Data Catalogue:** GeoNode provides a data catalogue in which data is registered together with the corresponding meta data. The metadata is published via pycsw [6].

6.2.2. Whitebox Data Analysis Tool

The whitebox architecture diagram of the Data Analysis Tool is shown in Fig. 9. It consists of the following components:

- **Internal and external climate models:** For most of the indicators, several processing and/or modeling steps need to be performed to achieve the final result. These transformations like bias corrections, down-scaling or other arithmetic calculations differ for different indicators. Therefore, the various calculation steps will be separated into modules which can be chained in a flexible way. Depending on the user requirements, models can be incorporated into the CS platform as *internal* models or they can be connected as *external* services.
- **Model & indicator catalogue:** The model and indicator catalogue stores information about the available indicators regarding the necessary initialisation and modeling steps that need to be performed to calculate the indicator. The information are stored in separate JSON files for every indicator.
- **Temporary data storage:** Before the indicator calculation is initiated, a copy of the original data file is stored in the temporary data storage. All modifications that result from the subsequent processing are applied to this working copy such that the original data file stays untouched and can be used as a reference to the processed data at any stage of the modeling chain.

- **Orchestration Service:** The Orchestration Service reads the information from the model and indicator catalogue and initialises the chain of modeling steps that need to be performed for the indicator calculation. It calls the individual models consecutively and organises the access to the temporary data storage. For the implementation of the Orchestration Service, two possibilities are currently under discussion. On the one hand, a new workflow engine could be implemented by the platform developers in the form of a python framework. This option will imply a flexible development of the engine's functionality according to the particular needs of the CS platform. On the other hand, already available workflow engines like Argo Workflows [2] provide a large set of features out-of-the box. Further research and discussions with the stakeholders will be undertaken in the near future to come to a final conclusion in this respect.
- **OGC API Processes:** The interface of the Data Analysis Tool to the GeoNode web framework is implemented as an OGC API Processes. Via this interface, the calculation of a particular indicator can be requested. This choice to follow the open OGC standard enhances the interoperability and accessibility of the Data Analysis Tool.

7. Runtime View

The runtime view sketches the concrete behavior and interactions of the systems building blocks, to clarify how the building blocks of the system interact with users, neighbouring systems, and among themselves while handling operations and tasks. An architecture sequence diagram will be discussed to explain the typical interaction of the user with the system, composed by the following blocks which have been defined in more detail in Sect. 6 (going from left to right)

- WEB-GUI: the web interface towards the final user through which requests for visualisation of indicators can be directed to the system,
- Orchestration service: to dialogue with other components and activate the requested processing pipeline,
- catalogues of embedded and available indicators and models,
- components to manage data and tasks: data REST API, task manager, data ingestor, data storage
- climate models: devoted to perform requested calculations.

Hereafter an example of a runtime scenario is provided linked to the Italian LL, to convey a clear understanding of how the system's components perform their jobs and highlight the architectural relevance of the system beyond static models.

7.1. Runtime Scenario Italian LL

The climate service for the Italian Living Lab will be able to provide forecast data and indicators about the river discharge for the hydrological basins of Secchia River in the Emilia Romagna Region (north east of Italy). The climate service is co-designed and co-developed together with a wide range of public and private stakeholders (regional policy makers, industry, irrigation consortia and environmental agencies) in order to support them in taking sounder decisions on water management, particularly during drought periods. The Run-time of the ITA_LL climate service consist of a request from the user through the WEB GUI to deploy daily to weekly discharge forecasts in a river for upstream available services, upload local recorded discharge data from a gauging station and obtain downscaled river discharge forecasts for that station. The output generated by the climate services are deployed in form of graphs and tables resuming available data, time series forecasts and tailored performances, error and uncertainty metrics.

The diagram in Fig. 10 sketches the above described scenario with reference to the main building blocks and components

1. users interact with the service GUI and selects the variable/station and lead time of interest.

2. orchestrator receives request and drives it to the respective modules
3. Data processing modules receive data and format them to be ready for algorithm to perform forecast, formatted data are stored
4. formatted data are passed to the forecast algorithms (tuned of the selected station) that perform discharge forecast at selected lead times and sent back to the orchestrator
5. graph, tables, and performance metrics are calculated and passed for final visualization to the user through the GUI with ancillary information.

8. Deployment View

As described in Sect. 4, the CS architecture will be deployed in a cloud environment. Following the concept of functional decomposition, the individual modules will run in separate docker containers and they will be orchestrated by Kubernetes. Further details of the deployment – e.g. central logging facilities and exception handling – will be defined in the further course of the I-CISK project.

9. Conclusion and Outlook

This document summarises the current status of the CS platform that will be developed in the course of the I-CISK project. While building on well-established data providers like Copernicus and SHMI for climate model calculations, there is a strong focus on combining this information with local data and local knowledge to produce enhanced information products that are adapted to stakeholders needs. A respective first requirement analysis has been performed and corresponding quality criteria have been derived. Following up on this, the major building blocks of the planned infrastructure have been defined and designed.

The I-CISK CS platform will consist of two major modules: the Data Analysis Tool which will contain the necessary functionality for the climate model calculations and the GeoNode web framework which will implement the GUI and the REST API as well as functionality regarding data access and organisation. Both modules will be connected to a number of external services with varying access modes and the whole infrastructure will be deployed in a cloud.

As a next step, mock-up CS will be implemented for single LLs to test and refine the current concept of the system architecture. The evaluation of the possibilities for the implementation of the orchestration service will be brought to conclusion and it will be decided on a cloud service for the deployment. At the same time, efforts will be ongoing regarding the identification of the stakeholder requirements with respect to the visualisation of the modeling results. In this context, mock-up visualisation will be designed and refined in close collaboration with the stakeholders.

Figure 10: Architecture sequence diagram showing the runtime communication between the individual CS components for the Italian LL.

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A. Glossary

Acronym	Definition
AWS	Amazon Web Services
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CC	climate change
CDS	Copernicus Data Store
CEMS	Copernicus Emergency Management Service
CS	climate service
CSIS	climate-service infrastructure
GUI	Graphical User Interface
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
ECV	essential climate variable
KPI	key performance indicator
LL	living lab
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OS	operating system
OTC	Open Telekom Cloud
SMHI	Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute
WCS	Web Coverage Service
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
WFS	Web Feature Service
WMS	Web Map Service
WPS	Web Processing Service
API	Application Programming Interface
WP	I-CISK working package

I-CISK

HUMAN CENTRED CLIMATE SERVICES

Colophon:

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